

Temperature, osmotic and pH stress are associated with antibiotic susceptibility changes in *Staphylococcus aureus*

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Summary

The role of bacteria, especially *Staphylococcus aureus* in health and processing of food are inevitable. During food processing, bacteria are exposed to a variety of stresses and effect on bacterial physiology, which could be varied based on pathogen and nature of stress. The present study aimed to investigate the probable effect of some environmental stresses on the antibiotic susceptibility of *S. aureus* toward different antibiotic.

Resistant subpopulation of *S. aureus* ATCC 25923 was selected by exposure to different environmental stresses and subjected for further analysis. The antibiotic susceptibility of unstressed

(control) and stressed *S. aureus* strain was performed by the disk diffusion method. Sodium dodecyl sulfate-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) was used to analyze the pooled proteins from each condition.

Antibiotic susceptibility results revealed all unstressed strains were susceptible to tested agents, while stressed isolated showed a different susceptibility pattern. In general, acid, alkaline and cold stresses were associated with increasing the resistance to tested antibiotics. However, high temperature and osmotic pressure by glucose concentration were mostly associated with increased susceptibility to antibacterial agents. Analysis of SDS-PAGE results showed protein profile changes in stressed cells compared to unstressed strain.

In summary, our results indicated that *S. aureus* strains could undeniably tolerant wide range of environmental stresses and successfully growth after stress elimination. Moreover, we found that survived stressed *S. aureus* are mostly associated with changes in antibiotic susceptibility.

Key words

Staphylococcus aureus, Antibiotic susceptibility, Environmental stress, SDS-PAGE

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Introduction

The role of microorganisms, especially bacteria in health and processing of food are inevitable.^{1,2} Some of these bacteria regarded as safe organism and can be directly consumed as probiotic or used of their secondary metabolisms such as fermentation products; instead, some are undesirable microorganisms.^{1,3} *Staphylococcus aureus* is a nonmotile facultative anaerobic Gram-positive coccus which well known for their role in food microbiology as a common cause of food poisoning.⁴⁻⁶ Bacterial food poisoning is defined as diseases or intoxication that results from the consumption of food or water containing pathogen agents or their toxic compounds.⁷ *S. aureus* produces a wide range of extracellular proteins and enterotoxins that contribute to gastrointestinal diseases.⁷⁻⁹

One the important aspect of food safety is control of microorganisms.¹⁰ During food processing bacteria

are exposed to a variety of stresses and since food quality is important in this process, they may expose to both lethal and sub-lethal stresses.¹¹ As a fundamental concept from previous studies, environmental stresses such as seen in food processing effect on bacterial physiology, which could be varied based on pathogen and nature of stress.^{12,13} One of the main concerns about the impact of environmental stresses on bacteria is altering susceptibility to antibacterial agents.^{12,14} It has been documented that the adaptive responses to environmental stresses with a mechanism that called as cross-protection may enhance resistance to antibiotics.¹⁵ In this way, previously in two separate studies, Ganjian *et al.*, and Al-Nabulsi *et al.*, mentioned to role of salt stress as the cause of the antimicrobial resistance changes in bacterial isolates.^{15,16}

Antibiotic resistance is a growing problem and has an important role in infection control policies, especially in food processing, since resistance gene could

easily transfer among bacterial isolates.¹⁷⁻¹⁹ Moreover, control of these unwanted outcomes during food processing has an important social and economic justification. Therefore, in the present study, we aimed to investigate the probable effect of some environmental stresses on the antibiotic susceptibility of *S. aureus* toward different antibiotics.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Bacterial strain and Stress conditions

The strain used in the present study was an *S. aureus* ATCC 25923 which obtained from the Iranian Research Organization for Science and Technology. A 24 h fresh culture (exponential phase) was prepared by *S. aureus* inoculation into the tube containing trypticase soy broth (TSB; Merck, Germany) with a final concentration at a density equivalent to 0.5 McFarland standard. Then resistant subpopulation of *S. aureus* strain was selected from original population by exposure to glucose 15, 25 and 35% (wt/vol); acidified with 1M HCL to the value of 2, 3 and 4 pH; alkaline with 1M NaOH to value of 9, 11, 13 pH; heated in a water bath to 85, 95 and 100°C and cooled to -4, 7 and 25°C for 10 min to achieve desired stress conditions. All chemical products (Glucose, HCL, and NaOH) was purchased from Merck, Germany. As well, control samples investigated in previous introduced suspensions at pH 7 and incubation temperature 37°C. Finally, control and stressed suspensions were harvested by centrifugation at 2500 g for 15 min and resuspended in 10 mL TSB and incubated at 37°C for 24 h and then reached to desired concentration for further tests.

2.2 Antibiotic susceptibility testing and protein analysis

Cell suspensions containing stressed and normal bacterial cells were plated on Mueller-Hinton agar (MHA; Merck, Germany) plates using a sterile swab. Susceptibility against 11 antibiotics was tested by performing the disk diffusion method (MAST Diagnostics, Merseyside, UK) according to the Clinical Laboratory Standards Institute guidelines (CLSI).²⁰ The antibiotics used and their disk potencies were as follows: erythromycin 15µg (E); penicillin G 10U (PG), gentamicin 10µg (GM), ciprofloxacin 5µg (CIP), cefalexin 30µg (CFX), chloramphenicol 30µg (C); co-trimoxazole 25µg (SXT), rifampicin 5µg (RP), clindamycin 2µg (CD), cephalothin 30µg (CF) and methicillin 25µg (MT). The plates were incubated at 37°C for 18 h and were then examined 4 times for the development of zones of inhibition in each lawn growth around the disc. The pooled protein from stressed and un-stressed (control) cells were analyzed using sodium dodecyl sulfate poly-

acrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) as previously described by Laemmli.²¹

2.3 Statistical analysis

The analysis was performed by using SPSS™ software, version 21.0 (IBM Corp., USA). The results are presented as descriptive statistics in terms of relative frequency. Values were expressed as the mean ± standard deviation (continuous variables) or percentages of the group (categorical variables). Statistical analyses were performed using unpaired *t* tests and a *P* value <0.05 considered to be statistically significant.

3. Results

Antibiotic susceptibility results revealed all unstressed strains were susceptible to tested agents, while stressed isolated showed a different susceptibility pattern.

Acid stressed strains, especially at pH 2 showed decreased in their susceptibility toward the most of the antibiotics i.e. rifampicin, clindamycin, ciprofloxacin, cefalexin and methicillin (Table 1). Stressed strains which exposed to pH 2 become moderately resistant against clindamycin and ciprofloxacin. Moreover, pH 3 caused stressed strains become moderately resistant to clindamycin. However, acid stresses were associated with increasing susceptibility to penicillin, co-trimoxazole and chloramphenicol antibiotics compared to unstressed strains.

In overall, alkaline stresses were associated with reducing the susceptibility to tested antibiotics; however, some variation towards different antibiotics observed. Stressed strains at pH 12 and 13 become moderately resistant to clindamycin and at pH 13 strains were resistant to rifampicin. In other hand, exposed to pH 13 were associated with more susceptibility to chloramphenicol, cefalexin and co-trimoxazole (Table 1).

A notable increase of antibiotic resistance was seen in front of cold stressed strains. All cold stressed strains become resistant to penicillin. Moreover, at -7°C strains become moderately resistant and at 4 and 25°C become resistant to rifampicin. All cold stressed strains showed moderately resistance to clindamycin and same pattern for erythromycin except 25°C. Exposed to -7 and 4°C stresses were associated with resistant and moderately resistant to cefalexin, respectively. However, cold stressed strains showed more susceptible to some antibiotics with decreased of temperature (Table 2).

High temperature stresses were mostly associated with higher susceptibility to antibacterial agents. However, increasing temperature up to 100°C was asso-

Table 1 Mean zone of inhibition for acid and alkaline stressed strains^a

13	12	11	Control (un-stressed)	4	3	2	pH Antibiotic
16±3.5 (R)*	21±3*	22±2.9	25±1	25±4.1	22±3.2	19±2.7*	RIP
31±1.1	34±1	36±5	32±1	34±2.6	34±3.8	35±3.3	PG
19±2.5 (I)	19±1.1 (I)	21±1	21±1	21±1.5	19±3.8 (I)	17±4.8 (I)	CD
18±2.9	18±2.9	19±1	19±1	20±1	20±1	19±1	GM
21±1	24±1	22±2.6	22±1	24±2.5	23±1	22±2.4	E
25±0**	25±0**	25±1.4*	21±1	24±2*	25±1.3*	24±1.5*	SXT
28±4	29±5.3	34±3.4	30±1	32±2.1	30±4.5	27±8.6	CF
25±1	25±0	24±1.1	24±1	22±1.7	20±1*	19±2.5 (I)*	CIP
26±1.1*	26±1.1*	26±1*	22±1	25±0*	23±2.4	21±2	CFX
25±1.9*	24±1.3**	24±1.7*	19±1	22±1.7*	23±4.8	21±3.2	C
31±2.5	32±2.4	33±2.1	32±1	23±3.5*	22±4.3*	19±2**	MT

^aDiameter of inhibition zone presented as millimeters (mm) ± SD
^bI: intermediate- resistance; R; resistance
* P value <0.05; ** P value <0.001 (compared to control)

Table 2 Mean zone of inhibition for high temperature and cold stressed strains^a

100	90	80	Control (un-stressed)	25	4	-7	°C Antibiotic
30±3.1*	29±4.2	26±3.4	25±1	13±4.4 (R)*	14±4.3 (R)*	17±3.5 (I)*	RIP
35±2.1*	29±2*	24±2.3 (R)**	32±1	20±1.1 (R)**	24±1.5 (R)**	22±2.9 (R)**	PG
16±2.3 (I)*	17±3.2 (I)	19±2.6 (I)	21±1	19±1.2 (I)*	17±2.4 (I)*	16±3.2 (I)*	CD
20±2.4	20±2.9	20±1.9	19±1	17±2.2	20±4.2	21±3.3	GM
22±2.2	22±2.4	22±1.9	22±1	19±2.4	17±2.3 (I)*	18±2.6 (I)*	E
28±1.9**	27±2.8*	24±2.1*	21±1	19±2.2	22±2.4	24±1.1*	SXT
38±1.8**	37±1.9**	36±1.5**	30±1	24±1.7**	24±1.2**	23±2.3*	CF
22±1.1*	23±1.7	22±1.1*	24±1	21±1.9*	24±1.5	26±2.1	CIP
21±1.8	21±1.8	21±1.5	22±1	18±2.3*	15±1 (I)**	14±1.1 (R)**	CFX
26±3.3*	26±3.3*	23±3*	19±1	19±2.8	21±2.7	22±2.9	C
37±1.3**	33±2.4	31±1.5	32±1	30±1.1*	29±4.2	22±2.6**	MT

^aDiameter of inhibition zone presented as millimeters (mm) ± SD
^bI: intermediate- resistance; R; resistance
* P value <0.05; ** P value <0.001 (compared to control)

Table 3 Mean zone of inhibition for osmotic pressure stressed strains a^a

Control (un-stressed)	35%	25%	15%	Glucose
				Antibiotic
25±1	27±1.4	25±1.6	23±1.3	RIP
32±1	40±3.1*	38±3.2*	37±2.6*	PG
21±1	23±1.6	21±1.5	21±1	CD
19±1	19±1.2	19±1	20±1.2	GM
22±1	22±1.3	22±1.3	23±1.7	E
21±1	24±1.9*	23±1.3	22±2.1	SXT
30±1	38±3.4*	35±3.2*	34±3.5	CF
24±1	22±1.9	22±1.1	23±1.5	CIP
22±1	25±2.1	24±2.2	22±2.6	CFX
19±1	20±2.1	20±2.1	19±1.5	C
32±1	26±2.1*	27±1.8*	36±2.7*	MT

^aDiameter of inhibition zone presented as millimeters (mm) ± SD
* P value <0.05; ** P value <0.001 (compared to control)* P value <0.05;
** P value <0.001 (compared to control)

ciated with moderately resistant to clindamycin. Moreover, stressed strains at 85°C become resistant to penicillin (Table 2).

The effect of osmotic pressure that induced by different concentration of glucose was mostly associated with an increase of susceptibility to tested antibiotics and any notable changes in resistance pattern of stressed strains were not documented. All stressed strains at 35% glucose concentration become more susceptible to antibiotic agents except to ciprofloxacin and methicillin which susceptibility decreased compared to unstressed strains (Table 3). Analysis of SDS-PAGE results showed in Figure 1-3, respectively. In overall, protein profile changes were significant in pooled proteins of stressed cells compared to unstressed strain.

4. Discussion

Environmental stresses such as high or low temperature, osmotic and acid are among the most common food preservation procedures used in the food industry.¹⁰ However, induced mutation in bacterial cells has been associated with the development of ada-

pting strains which may show different properties with those unstressed strains.²² For example, *S. aureus* is killed rapidly at pH 2, but could develop resistance if adapted firstly and acid adapted cells were associated with a higher tolerated pH.²³ Antibiotic resistance is common reports of adverse consequence of environmental stresses on bacterial isolates.^{12,15,16} In the present study, acid stress caused reducing susceptibility of *S. aureus* toward the most of tested antibiotics. In support of our findings McMahan *et al.*, showed that acid stress increased antibiotic resistance among bacterial isolates included *S. aureus*.²⁴

In the presence of alkaline stress same as results of acid stress, stressed cells showed higher resistance than unstressed strains to the most of antibiotics. These results were similar to those of Al-Nabulsi *et al.*, who found that the resistance of bacterial strains to various antibiotics increased after exposure to alkaline stress.¹²

In our results, cold stress mainly increased bacterial antibiotic resistance and was most effective stress associated with increasing resistant strains. Previously, in two separated studies noted that cold stress exposed strains of *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Cronobacter sakazakii* become more resistant than unstressed

strains.^{12,13} In contrast to our results, McMahon *et al.* showed under low temperature stress, *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella enterica* serovar Typhimurium, and *S. aureus* strains become more susceptible to antibiotics than unstressed strains.²⁴

Heat stressed strains with some variation showed increasing susceptibility to the most of antibiotics. McMahon *et al.* closest to our finding mentioned that antibiotic susceptibility in *E. coli*, *S. enterica* serovar Typhimurium, and *S. aureus* increased when these organisms were subjected to high temperature stress.²⁴ Although, it was documented that heat stress increase antibiotic resistance in *C. sakazakii* strains.¹²

Osmotic stress by high levels of NaCl commonly reported in associated with higher antibiotic resistance,^{16,24} but in our findings osmotic stress which induced by glucose concentration did not show any significant increase of antibiotic resistance.

The uniform changes of antibiotic resistance of stressed *S. aureus* strains toward test antibiotic agents might be due to transient phenotypic changes such as cell membrane permeability, cell wall binding proteins, gene amplification or shock protein synthesis.^{3,10,13,25} These reasons may explain observed protein profile changes in stressed cells. However, further proteomics study need to specify the exact mechanism and position of protein profile alterations.

Finally, our study had some limitations which we would like to disclose. First, it was better that we compared our results with *S. aureus* strains obtained from food sources. Second, we could deploy a wider range of stress conditions.

Conclusion

In summary, beside of limitations our study has some notable outcomes. Our results indicated that *S. aureus* strains could undeniably tolerant wide range of environmental stresses and successfully growth after stresses elimination. Moreover, we found that survived stressed *S. aureus* strains are mostly associated with antibiotic susceptibility changes. However, fully understand of possible mechanisms of antibiotic susceptibility changes in stressed strains afford further studies with the aiming to investigate alterations of proteins and signaling mechanisms.

Acknowledgment

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Conflict of interest

None declared.

Figure 1 SDS-PAGE analysis of pooled proteins from un-stressed (Control) and stressed *S. aureus* strain. A: under cold stress; B: under heat stress.

Figure 2 SDS-PAGE analysis of pooled proteins from un-stressed (Control) and stressed *S. aureus* strain. A: under acid stress; B: under alkaline stress.

Figure 3

SDS-PAGE analysis of pooled proteins from un-stressed (Control) and stressed *S. aureus* strain under osmotic stress

Περίληψη

Θερμικό, ωσμωτικό και pH stress συνδέεται με μεταβολές στην ευαισθησία στα αντιβιοτικά του χρυσίζοντος σταφυλοκόκκου

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Ο ρόλος των βακτηρίων, ειδικά του χρυσίζοντος σταφυλοκόκκου (*Staphylococcus aureus*) στην υγεία και την παρασκευή των τροφών είναι αναμφισβήτητος: κατά τη διάρκεια της παρασκευής των τροφών τα βακτήρια εκτίθενται σε ποικιλία στρεσογόνων παραγόντων που επιδρούν στη φυσιολογία των βακτηρίων, που μπορεί να ποικίλουν ανάλογα με το παθογόνο και το είδος του stress.

Σκοπός της παρούσας μελέτης ήταν η διερεύνηση της πιθανής επίδρασης ορισμένων περιβαλλοντικών καταστάσεων stress στην αντιμικροβιακή ευαισθησία του *S. aureus* (έναντι) διαφορετικών αντιβιοτικών.

Ανθεκτικός υποπληθυσμός του *S. aureus* ATCC 25923 επιλέχθηκε με έκθεση σε διαφορετικά περιβαλλοντικά stresses και εξετάστηκε με περαιτέρω ανάλυση.

Η ευαισθησία στα αντιβιοτικά των στελεχών του *S. aureus* χωρίς stress (μάρτυρες) και των στελεχών υπό stress έγινε με τη μέθοδο των δίσκων διάχυσης. Sodium dodecyl sulfate – polyacrylamide και ηλεκτροφόρων γέλης (SDS-PAGE) χρησιμοποιήθηκε για την ανάλυση των συγκεντρωθέντων πρωτεϊνών από κάθε συνθήκη.

Η ευαισθησία στα αντιβιοτικά αποκάλυψε ότι όλα τα στελέχη χωρίς stress ήταν ευαίσθητα στους παράγοντες που δοκιμάστηκαν ενώ τα στελέχη υπό stress παρουσίαζαν διαφορετικό τύπο ευαισθησίας. Γενικά όξινα, αλκαλικά και τα stress ψύχους συνδέονται με αύξηση της αντοχής στα αντιβιοτικά δοκιμασίας. Εντούτοις, υψηλή θερμοκρασία και ωσμωτική πίεση από συγκέντρωση γλυκόζης συνδέονται ως επί το πλείστον (κυρίως) με αυξημένη ευαισθησία σε αντιμικροβιακούς παράγοντες. Ανάλυση των αποτελεσμάτων της SDS-PAGE-PATTERN έδειξε μεταβολές στο προφίλ των κυττάρων υπό stress συγκριτικά με εκείνο του χωρίς stress στελέχους.

Συμπερασματικά, τα αποτελέσματα δείχνουν ότι στελέχη του *S. aureus* δύνανται αναμφισβήτητα να είναι ανθεκτικά –σε ευρύ φάσμα ανθίστανται–, να αντέχουν stress από το περιβάλλον και να αναπτύσσονται επιτυχώς μετά την εξάλειψη του stress. Επιπλέον διαπιστώθηκε ότι τα επιβιώσαντα στελέχη του *S. aureus* υπό stress κυρίως συνδέονται με μεταβολές στην ευαισθησία στα αντιβιοτικά.

Λέξεις κλειδιά

Χρυσίζοντας σταφυλόκοκκος, Αντιβιοτική ευαισθησία, Περιβαλλοντολογικό stress, SDS-FACE

References

- Gobbetti M, Cagno RD, De Angelis M. Functional microorganisms for functional food quality. *Crit Rev Food Sci Nutr*. 2010;50: 716-27.
- Khashei R, Malekzadegan Y, Sedigh Ebrahim-Saraie H, Razavi Z. Phenotypic and genotypic characterization of macrolide, lincosamide and streptogramin B resistance among clinical isolates of staphylococci in south-west of Iran. *BMC Res Notes*. 2018;11: 711.
- Cotter PD, Hill C. Surviving the acid test: responses of gram-positive bacteria to low pH. *Microbiol Mol Biol Rev*. 2003;67: 429-53, table of contents.
- Nejabat M, Khashei R, Bazargani A, Sedigh Ebrahim-Saraie H, Motamedifar M. Evaluation of High-Level of Mupirocin Resistance among Clinical Isolates of Methicillin-Resistant Staphylococcus aureus from Shiraz, Iran (2008-2009). *Pharm Sci*. 2015;21: 225-8.
- Le Loir Y, Baron F, Gautier M. Staphylococcus aureus and food poisoning. *Genet Mol Res*. 2003;2: 63-76.
- Ebrahim-Saraie HS, Heidari H, Khashei R, Edalati F, Malekzadegan Y, Motamedifar M. Trends of antibiotic resistance in staphylococcus aureus isolates obtained from clinical specimens. *J Krishna Inst Med Sci*. 2017; 6: 19-30.
- Argudin MA, Mendoza MC, Rodicio MR. Food poisoning and Staphylococcus aureus enterotoxins. *Toxins (Basel)*. 2010;2: 1751-73.
- Shahini Shams-Abadi M, Halaji M, Hoseini-Alfatemi SM, Gholipour A, Mojtahedi A, Sedigh Ebrahim-Saraie H. Epidemiology of toxic shock syndrome toxin-1 harboring Staphylococcus aureus obtained from clinical samples in Iran: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *Ann Ig*. 2018;30: 391-400.
- Shahini Shams Abadi M, Nikokar I, Hoseini Alfatemi SM, Malekzadegan Y, Azizi A, Sedigh Ebrahim-Saraie H. Epidemiology of Panton-Valentine Leukocidin harbouring Staphylococcus aureus in cutaneous infections from Iran: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Infez Med*. 2017;25: 217-23.
- Beales N. Adaptation of microorganisms to cold temperatures, weak acid preservatives, low pH, and osmotic stress: a review. *Comprehensive reviews in food science and food safety*. 2004;3: 1-20.
- Davidson PM, Harrison MA. Resistance and adaptation to food antimicrobials, sanitizers, and other process controls. *Food Technol*. 2002;56: 69-78.
- Al-Nabulsi AA, Osaili TM, Elabedeen NA, et al. Impact of environmental stress desiccation, acidity, alkalinity, heat or cold on antibiotic susceptibility of Cronobacter sakazakii. *Int J Food Microbiol*. 2011; 146: 137-43.
- Capozzi V, Fiocco D, Amodio ML, Gallone A, Spano G. Bacterial stressors in minimally processed food. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2009;10: 3076-105.
- Nikokar I, Ebrahim-Saraie HS, Ganjian H. Variations in Antibiotic Susceptibility Profile of Staphylococcus aureus after Povidone-Iodine Stress. *Pharm Sci*. 2017;23: 72-6.
- Al-Nabulsi AA, Osaili TM, Shaker RR, et al. Effects of osmotic pressure, acid, or cold stresses on antibiotic susceptibility of Listeria monocytogenes. *Food Microbiol*. 2015;46: 154-60.
- Ganjian H, Nikokar I, Tieshayar A, Mostafaei A, Amir-mozafari N, Kiani S. Effects of Salt Stress on the Antimicrobial Drug Resistance and Protein Pattern of Staphylococcus aureus. *Jundishapur J Microbiol*. 2012;5: 328-31.
- Motamedifar M, Ebrahim-Saraie HS, Alfatemi SM, Zalipour M, Kaveh M, Khoshkharam-Roodmajani H. Frequency of the toxic shock syndrome toxin-1 gene in methicillin-susceptible and -resistant Staphylococcus aureus isolates from teaching hospitals in Shiraz, Iran. *Rev Soc Bras Med Trop*. 2015;48: 90-3.
- Hennekinne JA, De Buyser ML, Dragacci S. Staphylococcus aureus and its food poisoning toxins: characterization and outbreak investigation. *FEMS Microbiol Rev*. 2012;36: 815-36.
- Zalipour M, Ebrahim-Saraie HS, Sarvari J, Khashei R. Detection of biofilm production capability and icaA/D genes among staphylococci isolates from Shiraz, Iran. *Jundishapur J Microbiol*. 2016;9: 1-7.
- Wayne PA. Performance Standards for Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing. *Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI)*. 2016;26th Informational Supplement:
- Laemmli UK. Cleavage of structural proteins during the assembly of the head of bacteriophage T4. *Nature*. 1970;227: 680-5.
- Poole K. Bacterial stress responses as determinants of antimicrobial resistance. *J Antimicrob Chemother*. 2012;67: 2069-89.
- Huws SA, Smith AW, Enright MC, Wood PJ, Brown MR. Amoebae promote persistence of epidemic strains of MRSA. *Environ Microbiol*. 2006;8: 1130-3.
- McMahon MA, Xu J, Moore JE, Blair IS, McDowell DA. Environmental stress and antibiotic resistance in food-related pathogens. *Appl Environ Microbiol*. 2007;73: 211-7.
- Rahmati-Bahram A, Magee JT, Jackson SK. Effect of temperature on aminoglycoside binding sites in Stenotrophomonas maltophilia. *J Antimicrob Chemother*. 1997;39: 19-24.

